

Primer: Systematic Reviews

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What is a systematic review?

A systematic review of the literature aims to identify all available evidence, published or unpublished, for a specific research question. It is of great value for health care providers, researchers, and policy makers ([Mulrow, 1994](#)), and helps to generate reliable, generalizable, and reproducible evidence. Guidelines for the conduct and reporting of systematic reviews, as well as on risk of bias assessment exist ([Page et al., 2021](#); [Whiting et al., 2016](#)).

Examples

While systematic reviews are most well-known in the context of the evaluation of interventions in randomized controlled trial (RCT) settings, systematic reviews can also be performed on data collected in other study designs, e.g. in observational cohort studies or prognostic/diagnostic studies, or combinations thereof. In these situations, research questions will be different, the underlying data sets may be larger, they represent real-world evidence, and there will probably be larger between-study heterogeneity. In the following we present a few examples of systematic reviews for different research questions.

In a recently developed [guideline](#) for diagnosis and management of hypertension in adults by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), a systematic review was conducted, including RCTs and systematic reviews. Its review protocol was published on PROSPERO ([CRD42018087407](#)). An example of a systematic review on observational data in children operated for congenital heart disease was recently [published](#) to evaluate cognitive and executive function outcomes at school-age and to identify risk factors for unfavourable outcome ([Feldmann et al., 2021](#)). It is obvious that no randomized trial design is appropriate for the included individual studies in this area of research. As an example for a systematic review on prognostic or diagnostic studies, a [systematic evaluation](#) of the literature and critical appraisal was conducted to identify prediction models for diagnosis and prognosis of covid-19 ([Wynants et al., 2020](#)). A common difficulty in most systematic reviews is the insufficient reporting quality and/or sub-optimal conduct of the included studies, leading to low levels of evidence.

Ten steps to conduct a systematic review

Conducting a systematic review requires diligence and some time. However, the necessary tasks to conduct a rigorous systematic review are mostly straightforward. Here we present ten steps to conduct and also to critically appraise a systematic review (Figure 1).

Step 1: Define a specific research question

Formulating a focused research question is among the most critical tasks for a systematic review. Based on this, clinical systematic reviews commonly use the PICO framework to define a research question, i.e., **P**atients/**P**opulation, **I**ntervention; **C**omparison; **O**utcomes. For example, what is the effect of opicinumab (I) on myelin repair (O) in multiple sclerosis (P) compared to placebo (C)? A common pitfall during this step is having an ill-defined research question. Preliminary searches using relevant keywords, e.g., in Pubmed, can mitigate the problem whether Will there be likely 50'000 publications or only five? ([PubMed](#)).

Figure 1: The ten steps to conduct a rigorous systematic review and potential pitfalls per step.

Step 2: Define your systematic review team

At a bare minimum, the team should comprise two researchers to enable independent abstract and full text screening as well as data extraction and risk of bias assessment. Yet it is better to involve additional expertise from different fields, e.g., a systematic review methodologist, a librarian (for creating comprehensive literature searches, step 4), and potentially a (bio-)statistician (for meta-analysis).

Step 3: Write and register a protocol

A priori writing and registration of a systematic review protocol is a critical step for conducting a rigorous systematic review. Such a systematic review protocol pre-defines the employed review methodology, e.g., in- and exclusion criteria for references or data to extract. This is to avoid making subjective/non-reproducible choices based on which publications are in- or excluded and hence to minimize bias (Egger et al., 2022). Different web-based platforms can be used to register such a protocol; the most commonly used option is the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO). Of note, PROSPERO and Cochrane protocols should be checked for similar systematic reviews to avoid unnecessary duplication of work. The protocol should contain information on the systematic review question(s), strategies how to screen abstracts, in- and exclusion criteria for references, outcome measures to extract, the strategy for data synthesis, and other. Of note, protocols for clinical and preclinical systematic reviews do slightly differ (de Vries et al., 2015). PROSPERO provides entry masks for both domains.

Step 4: Conduct a comprehensive literature search

A sound literature search for a systematic review should be both reproducible and comprehensive. The search strategy has to be meticulously documented. This is not only important for potential later update searches but also for other groups to potentially reproduce the search. A broad variety of biomedical databases can be searched, most prominently MEDLINE (e.g., via Pubmed or Ovid), EMBASE, Scopus, or Web of Science. Additional data bases with more dedicated content can be searched, e.g., for randomized clinical trials (COCHRANE). These data bases are only partly overlapping. Thus,

it is important that the search encompasses at least two and ideally more relevant data bases. Another pitfall to consider is the use of multiple synonyms for each concept during data base search (Egger et al., 2003). Furthermore, each data base has different functionalities and syntax. Hence, it is highly recommended to involve an information specialist for this task. Most academic libraries offer such support for comprehensive searches for systematic reviews. Other sources of eligible references can be considered for systematic reviews such as grey literature, i.e., material not indexed by major databases, for example conference proceedings or trial registries. A pitfall during this step is to have an insufficiently sensitive search strategy which can result in key studies being missed. An approach to mitigate this problem is to define benchmark studies. These are studies which are likely eligible for the systematic review. These benchmark studies should all be detectable by the respective search string.

Step 5: Screen abstracts independently

The references identified in step 4 must be screened for eligibility based on titles and abstracts. At least two reviewers should screen these references independently, that is blinded to the decision of the other reviewer. Discrepancies between these two reviewers can either be resolved by discussion or by a third reviewer. A variety of online tools is available for abstract screening (Harrison et al., 2020), among them Covidence, Rayyan, or SyRF each of them with individual strengths and weaknesses (Kellermeyer et al., 2018). Of note, screening the titles and abstracts of identified studies is among the most labor-intensive steps of a systematic review (Bannach-Brown et al., 2019). Even though so far mostly used in experimental settings, data-driven approaches using artificial intelligence-based methods can be leveraged to expedite abstract sorting from large literature corpora (Gates et al., 2019; van de Schoot et al., 2021).

Step 6: Screen full texts independently

The full texts of potentially eligible references, as identified in step 5, will be scrutinized by two independent reviewers. This is particularly important for records in which the title and/or abstract provided ambivalent information on eligibility. EndNote provides a full text fetch function which is able to automatically find most of the full texts available through institutional licences.

An example for a PRISMA flowchart applied to observational studies, based on the systematic review on children with congenital heart disease, is given in Figure 2.

Step 7: Extract data independently

For references which remain eligible after full text screening, data will be extracted as pre-defined in the protocol. Like abstract and full text screening, data should be extracted by two independent reviewers. Google Sheets provides a free web-based spreadsheets for independent data extraction. A common pitfall during this step is insufficient characterization of parameters to extract, e.g., just labelling a column “n”. Using such an unequivocal nomenclature commonly leads to confusion during later time points when revisiting the extraction sheet. Hence, we recommend to add a dedicated row with meta-data to the spreadsheet with further explanations, e.g., “number of subjects in the treatment group”.

Step 8: Assess the risk of bias

Methodological characteristics of eligible studies are of high relevance for the systematic review (Egger et al., 2022). Concretely, methodologically flawed studies could lead to misleading conclusions. Thus, it is recommended to assess risk of bias of eligible studies (Hooijmans et al., 2014; Sena et al., 2014; Boutron et al., 2019). Bias refers to a systematic distortion of study results/conclusions. For example, absence of blinding or randomization in preclinical and clinical studies can induce biases leading to over- or underestimation of effects. A variety of different risk of bias assessment tools has been

Figure 2: Example of a PRISMA flowchart describing the process of searching and including studies into the meta-analysis (Feldmann et al., 2021). Figure reproduced with permission from American Academy of Pediatrics.

developed. For human studies, commonly used tools include the Cochrane risk of bias tool for randomized trials (Higgins et al., 2011) or the Joanna Briggs Institute critical appraisal tools (JBI appraisal tools). For animal studies, a commonly used tool is the SYRCLE risk of bias tool which is based on the Cochrane risk of bias tool (Hooijmans et al., 2014).

Step 9: Draw conclusions from your data

The goal of this step is to answer the initially posed research question as pre-defined in the protocol. To achieve this, all review authors should confer, ideally with knowledge about the extracted data as well as the risk of bias.

It is possible that the initially posed research question cannot be answered by the available evidence. Nevertheless, the heterogeneity of the field can still be probed and important insights into ambiguous research areas or what is unknown within a certain research area can be gained. Of note, a meta-analysis, i.e., a statistical approach to pool effect sizes from different studies to calculate an overall effect, can also be part of a systematic review. Due to the comprehensive nature of this topic, we refer to other resources (Egger et al., 2022).

Step 10: Make your systematic review publicly available

It is important to make your systematic review publicly available, independent from what the outcome was (Ioannidis, 2016). This is not only to mitigate publication bias but also to inform colleagues about your study to avoid unnecessary duplication of work. The PROSPERO protocol should also be updated upon publication of your manuscript. The PRISMA guidelines (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) are formal guidelines on how to report clinical (Page et al., 2021) and preclinical systematic reviews (Lalu et al., 2020).

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